

FORMATION OF THE PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF THE FUTURE PHYSICAL CULTURE TEACHER

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Abstract. *This article describes the development of professional training of future physical culture teachers, the technology of forming their educational activities, the ways of forming their knowledge, skills, qualifications and creating pedagogical competence.*

Key words: *physical education teacher, educational activity, formation of educational activity, systematic approach, technology of formation of educational activity.*

ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОЙ ПОДГОТОВКИ БУДУЩЕГО УЧИТЕЛЯ ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассмотрены вопросы развития профессиональной подготовки будущих учителей физической культуры, технологии формирования их учебной деятельности, пути формирования у них знаний, умений, навыков и формирования педагогической компетентности.*

Ключевые слова: *учитель физической культуры, учебная деятельность, формирование учебной деятельности, системный подход, технология формирования учебной деятельности.*

The problem of forming the educational activity of the future teacher traditionally attracts the attention of experts in the field of psychology and pedagogy of higher education. It is studied not only as a subject of independent review, but also as part of the study of related problems to one degree or another: continuity of higher and secondary schools, adaptation of secondary school graduates to conditions of higher education, continuation of secondary school students in secondary educational institutions, adaptation of secondary school graduates to educational conditions in higher educational institutions, secondary education ensuring the integrity of the activities of lim schools. formation of components of students' educational work, organization of independent work of students and formation of their readiness for self- education, individualization of education in higher educational institutions, etc. Such a wide field of research, on the one hand, speaks of a deep study of the problem under discussion, and on the other hand, it testifies to its inexhaustible relevance.

This is natural at the junction of two qualitatively different educational systems, each of which has its own unique form and methods of educational work. The analysis shows that the general education school does not adequately prepare its graduates to continue their studies at the university, the general level of preparation of school students is low and there is no tendency to increase it in the next five years. The school does not, and according to the existing education system, it cannot enslave a "ready" student. Academic activity of first-year students is mainly formed spontaneously, randomly and is accompanied by a significant decrease in academic efficiency and serious difficulties in the general educational nature. In the process of further education at the university, the majority of students will certainly adapt to the organizational and pedagogical features of higher education.

A control experiment and an analysis of scientific research literature show that special, targeted unemployed students become full subjects of educational activities only by the 3rd-4th year. At the same time, a large number of future teachers feel the consequences of the gaps and deformations that occurred at the initial stage of university education. Their learning activities are mainly formed by "trial and error", that is, in the most ineffective way. The culture of educational activity of such students is usually low, mainly irrational techniques and methods of teaching are used, the prospects of creative development of a specialist in professional activity are doubtful. According to our observations, most of the first-year teachers do not take into account the specific features of the initial stage of education in higher educational institutions in their methodological research. Nevertheless, the teachers who teach in the following courses believe that they are completely prepared to prepare students and teach their subjects without providing adequate explanations on how to master the learning material.

As a result of the surveys, we found out that even graduate students are not familiar with the concept of "learning activity" and do not fully understand the need for self-development in this regard. In the faculty of physical education, the situation is aggravated by the specific features of the educational process based on a number of features of future professional activity: - a wider educational space compared to the classroom; - diversity and complexity of the environment during classes; - a lot of equipment that can be life-threatening if misused; - high physical activity of students, fraught with the possibility of injury; - working with different age groups in one school day; - different levels of students' physical development and health status; - simultaneous conduct of classes with boys and girls, differences in assignments; - considerable expenditure of not only mental, but also physical energy; - increase in requirements for the educational and material base; - the difference in clothing from teachers of other subjects, etc. The above reasons, as well as combining educational activities with active sports, always maintaining a good physical shape, and frequent absences from related classes, deliberately put students of the Faculty of Physical Education in an unfavorable learning environment.

Thus, concluding this stage of the research, we can emphasize the relevance of the problem of formation of educational activities of the future physical culture teacher and the timely search for ways to solve it. There is an objective need to correct the educational process in terms of real readiness of school graduates to continue education at a new, more complex level. Methodological support plays an important role in the scientific study of educational activity and practical actions on its formation. First of all, it is necessary to consider the main category of research - educational activities. It should be said that its analysis can be done on different bases. At the same time, it is clear that one of the most influential directions in the science of psychological and pedagogy - the general theory of activity - is impossible not to mention. According to this theory, activity is a practical change of the objective world by a social person, and therefore, the change in the active subject itself takes place in the process of concrete activity, which differs according to the criteria of motives that motivate them. Actions - processes and operations subject to goals - methods of performing actions related to the conditions of their implementation are distinguished within the scope of activity. As a constitutive characteristic of activity, its objectivity is considered, which is manifested in the characteristics of mental reflection. Thus, educational activity is one of the main types of human activity that arises due to a special need to change the active subject, to change oneself in the educational process.

While conducting a structural analysis of students' educational activity, we rely on the general structure of human activity and the form developed in the general psychological theory of that activity. DBElkonin, VVDavydov, AKMarkova and others believe that educational activity repeats, repeats the structure of all human activities within it. In the most general examination of the structure of human activity, they distinguish three main links: motivational-indicative, central (executive) and control-evaluative. This basic model, VVDavydov, in each specific case, research should be properly oriented based on the characteristic features of the type of activity being studied. Interpreting this scheme in relation to the future teacher's educational activities, we distinguish the following components in it: motivational-valuable, meaningful, activity-practical and control-evaluation.

The analysis of dissertations and monographs on relevant topics shows that most authors rely on the above structural model in their scientific research. At the same time, many works, as a rule, are devoted to the development of any component of educational activity. Undoubtedly, the raised aspects of the problem are relevant and require in-depth development. But the fact is that in their disintegration, the integrity that was originally characteristic of educational activity by its status is lost. In our opinion, educational activity should be studied and formed not in the one-sidedness of certain components, but in their structural unity. Orientation to include various aspects of the analysis of educational activity into its holistic view is determined by a systematic approach, the main rules of which are aimed at integrative processes, synthesis of the whole. Learning activity cannot be reduced to one of the identified components: a complete learning activity is always their unity and interaction. They can turn into each other - these changes are the dynamics of educational activity and its property as a systematic object. It is easy to understand that such an interpretation differs from a comprehensive understanding of educational activities, as any process of acquiring knowledge, skills and competences, which is still widespread in practice. The uniqueness of the educational activity is that it is always connected with the student's entry into the new reality, assimilation of every aspect of it. Therefore, in our practical actions, we tried to develop not individual components of educational activity, but a complex of their interdependence and interaction.

The analysis of the existing directions of development of the raised problem revealed a very wide arsenal of ways to solve it. The main directions are as follows: strengthening the preparation of schoolchildren for higher educational institutions; activities of preparatory courses for applicants; development of special courses aimed at adapting newcomers to university teaching; formation of general educational skills within certain subjects. Each of these areas has its advantages and disadvantages. Together, they give a bright pedagogical picture. However, at the stage of theoretical analysis, it becomes clear that the preference for any of the ways in question is doomed to a previously limited effect. The fact is that separate activities (even if carefully prepared) are not a single, integrated system of targeted actions, but rather scattered fragments. In our opinion, it is appropriate to refer to the systematic approach here, to use it as a methodology at a certain scientific level. Educational activity is considered as a systematic object, and it is known that the study of the system is inseparable from the study of the conditions of its existence. And since the educational activity is not formed at once, but goes through several stages in its development with its own conditions, the technology of its formation should consist of several stages with appropriate goals and tasks. As the main means of achieving them, taking into account the dynamism and versatility of the studied phenomenon,

there is a logical and consistent combination of practically proven methods of shaping the educational activity of the future teacher. Such an approach to solving the problem allows not only to take into account the uniqueness of each stage of the work more fully, but also to make the most effective use of the accumulated scientific and practical experience.

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